

Natural Alkaloids (Caffeine, Theobromine and Theophylline) as Dielectric Capping Layers for Gold and Aluminum Gate Electrodes in Low Operating Voltage Organic Field-Effect Transistors

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Abstract—Three natural alkaloids: caffeine, theobromine and theophylline are reported for their application as dielectric layers in organic field effect transistors (OFETs) utilizing both gold and aluminum gate electrodes. After careful purification of the materials, a detailed analysis using x-ray diffraction spectroscopy (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), contact angle (CA), impedance spectroscopy, amplitude modulated kelvin probe force microscope (AM-KPFM) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) is performed. OFET devices operating at typical voltages between 2 and 4 V have been fabricated with the investigated alkaloid films processed via blade coating (caffeine) or vacuum processing (theobromine and theophylline). The dielectric properties of these three alkaloids are measured in impedance spectroscopy and negligible leakage currents are observed when deposited in thin films as dielectric layers in OFETs on aluminum electrodes. There is a high tendency of these molecules to crystallize and form uneven surfaces. When the thin film forming properties are carefully controlled, organic alkaloids can be employed in applications involving implantable, transient or even edible electronics.

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Index Terms—natural alkaloids, caffeine, theobromine, theophylline, organic dielectrics, organic field-effect transistors, green materials, natural materials, sustainable electronics.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE electronic revolution is advancing at the pace that surprises even the market forecast agencies in their year by year prediction of the upcoming decade [1], with the conservative estimate for 2030 putting the global market for printed, flexible and organic electronics at ~74 billion dollars. The major playgrounds of this market are expected to be the electronic displays, the printed sensors, the structural, flexible and stretchable electronics, the energy harvesting devices and the printed logics, whereas the niche applications for the electronics battleground are envisioned to be the wearable and the implantable electronics and sensors for biomedical applications [2]. All the above areas of research and technology have to conform to more stringent worldwide

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regulations on electronic waste and energy consumption management [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]. Today, the main focus of research worldwide lies exclusively on achieving high performance of materials and technologies [9], [10], neglecting the “green” aspects of energy input in the fabrication process, the materials choice, carbon footprint, recyclability, as well as the ecological impact of respective products at their end of lifecycle [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17]. Obtaining the coveted logo of compostability is definitely not a straightforward task, as the latest guidelines of European Union clearly demonstrate [18], [19]. Modern electronic circuits have currently the ability to function without any physical or chemical change and degradation even at elevated temperatures [20], [21], [22], [23], [24]. However, recently ‘transient’ devices that dissolve, disintegrate, degrade or otherwise physically disappear at triggered times or with controlled dissolution rates are getting more and more appealing to the scientific community [25], [26]. This is because the groups of either water-soluble or bodily fluids-solvable of “transient” electronic devices serve as the foundations for applications in environmental monitoring, ‘green’ consumer electronic gadgetry, bioresorbable medical implants [27], [28], [29], or simply medical implants with recording-transmission and biocompatibility capability [30], [31]. In this paper, we report a novel set of molecules as natural materials for electronics fabrication, *i.e.* natural alkaloids: caffeine, theobromine and theophylline. These molecules have a long history in science, being identified between 150 to 200 years ago [32], [33], [34], and have ever since become omnipresent in food as dietary supplements [35], [36], [37], [38]. In effect, theophylline, theobromine and caffeine occur freely in various plants (coffee, tea, cacao beans, guarana, mate, kola nuts) as a main source, as well as in trace amounts in 60 more plants. They have been consumed for thousands of years by humans, and with the advent of modern medicine, became employed also in the treatment of various medical conditions. Theobromine salts, *i.e.* calcium salicylate, sodium salicylate and sodium acetate were employed as coronary arteries dilator [39], [40], while newer studies consider theobromine as a safe chemical for consumption by humans, with fewer unwanted effects than caffeine [41]. Theophylline on the other hand has been used as a bronchodilator and for the treatment various airway diseases for over 80 years [42], and was recently shown to have anti-inflammatory effects in asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) when used in low concentrations [43], [44], [45]. Caffeine is a well-known psychostimulant compound with a long history of consumption by humans, dating back to China in 2737 B.C. [46], [47], [48]. Caffeine is nowadays the most widely consumed psychostimulant in the world, with more than 80% of the world population addicted to either daily or occasionally consumption of this substance [49]. When employed as medical implants or components of the

edible electronic capsules [50], [51] such organic electronic devices will offer not only the features of signal recording, processing and transmission, but also the safe resorbability of the implant and its beneficial therapeutic effects.

II. METHODS

A. Materials purification

Each of the three alkaloids were purified by two consecutive train sublimation steps, and the deposited material condensed on the colder end of the tube discarded. We employed for this process a procedure amply reported in our previous publication [52]. We attempted to deposit via vacuum deposition also the as-received materials (Sigma-Aldrich), but each of the three alkaloids splashed out of their respective crucible during thermal heating.

B. Structural characterization

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the powders of the three natural alkaloid materials, previously purified by two rounds of vacuum sublimation, were measured on a Bruker Vertex 80 FTIR spectrometer equipped with a Bruker Platinum attenuated total reflectance (ATR) unit. The spectra were measured with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} and averaging of 200 scans.

C. Electrochemical characterization

All experiments were conducted in a one-compartment setup, using an electrolyte solution containing 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆, >99.0%, Sigma Aldrich) in acetonitrile (anhydrous, Roth). Each natural alkaloid was evaporated onto ITO and used as a working electrode. A platinum wire was used as the counter electrode, while an Ag/AgCl electrode was used as the reference electrode. The measurements were recorded using an Ivium Vertex One. Potentiostat under a N₂ atmosphere at 50 mV/s. In all measurements, the first cycle of the CV was considered for the calculation of the band gaps, as dissolution of the material could be observed after the initial oxidation or reduction. All potentials are reported versus standard hydrogen electrode (SHE). The potential was recalculated using ferrocene (98%, Sigma Aldrich) as reference material and a redox potential of ferrocene of $E_{1/2} = 0.64\text{ V vs SHE}$ [53]. Onset potentials (E_{onset}) were determined by using the intercept point of the tangent in the half-step of the signal current and the baseline. The energy levels were calculated using a value of 4.75 eV of NHE vs. vacuum level [54]. In this work, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was used to determine the HOMO and LUMO levels. Here, the

material of interest is evaporated onto an ITO slide which is used as the working electrode in a three-electrode setup, with a Pt foil as counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl as quasi reference electrode. The method uses acetonitrile with tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate as electrolyte solution. The HOMO and LUMO are determined separately under forward bias, with the HOMO being attributed to the oxidation reaction and the LUMO being linked to the reduction reaction. The band edge is represented by the onset potential of the respective peak. The onset is defined as the intersection between the tangent passing through the point of inflection of the peak current and the base line. The onset potential is then calculated vs. SHE (standard hydrogen electrode) by calibrating with ferrocene. A redox potential of 0.64 V vs. SHE was used for ferrocene, as reported in literature [53]. Finally, the absolute energy levels can then be referenced against the vacuum level with 4.75 eV of SHE vs vacuum level.

D. X-ray diffraction characterization

The structural properties were investigated using a X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D8 advanced series) employing CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm).

E. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) and Amplitude Modulated Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy (AM-KPFM) characterization

Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) and Amplitude Modulated Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy (AM-KPFM) measurements of alkaloids films on chromium/gold (*i.e.* 10 nm Cr / 90 nm Au thickness) as well as 100 nm aluminum coated glass substrates were performed using Asylum Research MFP-3D AFM system. For AFM topography measurements, OMCL-AC160TS-R3 probes were used (spring constant 26 N/m, resonant frequency 300 kHz, tip radius ~ 7 nm). For AM-KPFM measurements, ASYELEC-01-R2 (Ti/Ir coating on both level reflection side and tip side) probes were used (spring constant 2.8 N/m, resonant frequency 75 kHz, tip radius 25 ± 10 nm). The topography information was acquired using AFM in tapping mode (with a scan speed of 15 $\mu\text{m/s}$). The results of contact potential differences (CPD) were obtained through AM-KPFM measurements in a two-pass mode, where the natural alkaloids films were grounded (at a scan speed of 5 $\mu\text{m/s}$, with the probe lifted by 10 nm during the second pass). Root mean square (RMS) data was calculated for both the topography roughness and the CPD fluctuations as an average with a standard deviation considering 3 arbitrarily chosen $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ areas of each sample. Topography and CPD images were processed in the open-source software Gwyddion v2.62 [55]. For topography

images, 1st-order line filtering was applied and leveling of the base plane. For CPD images, only zero-order line filtering was applied.

F. OFETs and MIM structures for impedance spectroscopy fabrication

We fabricated the dielectric films for metal-insulator-metal (MIM) and organic field-effect transistors (OFET) structures respectively, with the three alkaloid dielectrics processed as following: caffeine doctor bladed at a 2.5 mm/sec. blade speed from a 5 mg/ml solution in chloroform; theobromine and theophylline deposited by physical vapor deposition. We examined also the possibility to deposit theophylline from a 5 mg/ml solution in chloroform (its maximum solubility in chloroform is ~ 9 mg/ml), but the film forming was inferior to the one obtained after physical vapor deposition. Theobromine on the other hand is barely soluble in chloroform (solubility below 1 mg/ml) and the film quality significantly inferior to the vacuum deposited film. Theobromine as a matter of fact is well soluble in DMSO with a solubility limit ~ 30 mg/ml, however the high boiling point of the DMSO ($\sim 189^\circ\text{C}$) and the high crystallization tendency of theobromine, rendered the respective films unusable for further device fabrication. For both theobromine and theophylline, we pursued the vacuum deposition only in this study. We investigated also the deposition of caffeine from a 100 mg/ml precursor solution in chloroform as well as several rates of evaporation for theophylline and theobromine. We observed that the 100 mg/ml solution of caffeine in chloroform produces films with significant content of high crystallites (a topic described amply in the AM-KPFM section). Regarding the evaporation rate for theophylline and theobromine, we noticed that a rate of 0.1 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$. is the optimum one for the generation of layers of acceptable surface roughness for theophylline but a much lower rate (*i.e.* ~ 0.02 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$. – 0.03 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$.) is optimum for theobromine. The evaporation of theophylline and theobromine (~ 70 nm as dielectrics for OFETs and MIM structures) was done in a physical vapor deposition system (Edwards High Vacuum, Manor Royal, Crawley, Sussex), at a typical pressure of $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar, an evaporator dedicated in our laboratory explicitly to dielectrics sublimation [56], [57], [58]. Fullerene (C_{60}) and pentacene were employed as organic semiconductors; they have been deposited in 60 nm thick films at a rate of 0.1 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$ in individual square patterns for each of the four OFETs existent on one glass slide (as it is shown in the schematic of the fabrication masks, in Fig. 1S of the SI file accompanying the text of the article), in a Vaksis R&D Engineering evaporator at a typical pressure of $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar. 80 nm thick aluminum and gold electrodes for the C_{60} semiconductor and for the pentacene semiconductor respectively were evaporated in a physical vapor deposition instrument inside a glove box (Edwards AUTO 306 Vacuum Coater) at a rate of 0.1 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$.

The mask design of the source and drain contacts allowed us to pattern the respective electrodes with a length of the channel of 25 μm and the width of 2 mm, the width of the channel being in fact the same as the width of the gate electrode (see SI file, Fig. 2S). The two Edwards evaporators that we employed in this work are completely different and independent systems, one dedicated in our laboratory only to dielectrics deposition, and the other one to metal deposition, situated inside a glovebox under nitrogen. For this study we fabricated 3 batches of OFET devices (6 glass slides with 4 OFETs on each slide in one batch, see Fig. 2S) for each combination of dielectric-semiconductor, *i.e.* creating a pool of 72 OFETs for each pair (caffeine-pentacene, caffeine- C_{60} , *etc.*). This pool of samples is only for the reported values and graphs in this work, nevertheless our investigation of natural alkaloids was far more comprehensive, involving various deposition routes, *i.e.* spin coating from various solvents, blade coating at various blade speeds from 2.5 mm/sec to 25 mm/sec, vacuum processing at various deposition rates spanning from very low, *i.e.* $\sim 0.05 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec.}$ to high rates of 10 $\text{ \AA}/\text{sec.}$, with and without substrate heating. As can be seen in the text, the processing of the three natural alkaloids, caffeine, theobromine and theophylline is definitely not a straight forward task, mainly due to their low solubility in common organic solvents and their extreme tendency for crystallization. In addition, we investigated them as capping layers for hafnium oxide and tantalum oxide gate dielectrics, with hafnium and tantalum grown via sputtering deposition. Nevertheless, the results were inferior to those of the films deposited either on plain aluminum gates or on electrochemically grown aluminum oxide, and will not be elaborated in this report. For the study involving anodization of aluminum gate, we employed a setup consisting of a current-voltage source meter, Keithley 4ZA4 with the positive terminal connected to the active electrode (*i.e.* the aluminum gate layer to be anodized) and the negative terminal to the platinum reference electrode, in a citric acid bath. The concentration of the citric acid solution is absolutely critical for the quality of the electrochemically grown dielectric layer. We used a solution of identical concentration as previously reported by Mardare *et al.* [59], *i.e.* 0.265 g citric acid and 2.57 g sodium citrate in 100 ml deionized water producing a pH of ~ 6.0 . It is of paramount importance that the pH of the anodization solution be close to the neutral value, for obtaining a smooth and defect-free anodized layer of aluminum oxide. A typical thickness of the anodized layer is given by the equation [59]:

$$d = \alpha(V - V_{ox})$$

where α is the oxide forming factor, with a value of 1.6 for aluminum; V is the applied maximum voltage of anodization (*i.e.* 20 V and 8 V in our presented study) and V_{ox} is the voltage necessary to generate the native oxide (*i.e.* the layer that forms naturally when aluminum is exposed to ambient air), and has a value of $\sim 1.35 \text{ V}$ for aluminum. The thickness of spontaneously

oxidized aluminum surface exposed to ambient air has a typical thickness in the range of 1-1.5 nm and it may reach 2.6 nm as depending on the surface crystallography induced by the aluminum fabrication approach [60], [61]. The thickness of the electrochemically grown aluminum oxide is $\sim 11 \text{ nm}$ for the 8 V anodized and $\sim 33 \text{ nm}$ for the 20 V anodized alumina, respectively. The dielectric breakdown field experiment was performed for the alkaloids sandwiched between aluminum electrodes on the same gate electrode (see schematic in Fig. 2S) that hosted the 4 transistors measured in Fig. 12.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Alkaloids (“alkali-like” substances, a name introduced by the German chemist Carl Friedrich Wilhelm Meissner in the year 1819) are a class of basic, naturally occurring organic compounds that contain at least one nitrogen atom. The chemical structure of the three alkaloids investigated in this work is displayed in Fig. 1. The three molecules were purchased from Aldrich and purified by two consecutive train-sublimation procedures. The collected high purity materials had the appearance of very “shiny white crystals” for each of the three alkaloids, a completely different display from the original “white powders” form of the purchased precursor materials.

X-ray diffractograms were collected for the three alkaloids and a comparison was done for each material between the two times recrystallized powder used in this study and the precursor material purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Fig. 2 (panels (a) to (d)) shows such comparison, with the respective diffractogram lines clarified as captions inside each panel. It is clear that the purified materials and the precursor powders are one and the same, as panel (a) demonstrates in the case of caffeine. In panel (b), either thin or thick films of caffeine deposited by physical vapor deposition, and the corresponding solution processed film have the same major diffraction peaks that match well the one of the powders obtained by scraping off the film from the glass slide after its deposition by vacuum processing technique. Considering the fact that the material in the crucible was a 2-time purified caffeine, it made the powder whose diffractogram is displayed as green line in panel (b) as a 3-times purified caffeine, proving the fact that supplementary purification steps are not required for caffeine in particular. We decide to proceed with the 2-time purified materials for further investigations, for the entire set of alkaloids explored in this work, and not invest further time, effort and energy in successive purification steps⁵². In effect, the recorded X-ray diffractograms for the three alkaloids match well the values reported in the literature for these compounds [62], [63], [64]. Given their inner composition rich in moieties favorable to interact between adjacent molecules via hydrogen bonds (see Fig. 1 and the conclusions of Ref [62,63,64]), it is not surprising to find that the three alkaloids display crystalline and not amorphous morphology even when deposited in very thin films

as Fig. 2 clearly shows. This event, highlighted also by the AM-KPFM investigations will play a critical role in the OFETs fabrication and the reproducibility of the measurement results, that will be amply discussed in this article.

The electrochemical determination of the HOMO and LUMO levels for the three alkaloids can be found in Fig. 3. All three compounds show a similar reduction onset of around -0.6 V, as seen in Fig. 3. While caffeine and theobromine display one irreversible reduction peak, theophylline displays two well-defined cathodic peaks, with slight re-oxidation visible.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the caffeine, theobromine and theophylline.

Fig. 2. XRD spectra of investigated alkaloids, with characteristic peaks displayed on each graph: (a) caffeine “as-purchased” powder (Sigma Aldrich) and caffeine powder after its second sublimation; (b) comparison of various films of caffeine: thin and thick films deposited by physical vapor deposition; powder collected from the evaporation of caffeine, and caffeine deposited from solution in chloroform; (c) theobromine “as-purchased” powder (Sigma Aldrich) and theobromine powder after second sublimation; (d) theophylline “as-purchased” powder (Sigma Aldrich) and theophylline powder after second sublimation.

However, the absence of the re-oxidation peak and the severely diminished peak current is likely caused by the dissolution of the compound from the electrode upon reduction. In the oxidative regime, all three compounds show one distinct anodic peak, with slight re-reduction visible for caffeine and theobromine.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammetry of the investigated alkaloids: caffeine-black line, theobromine-red line and theophylline blue line.

Interestingly, the onset potential of the oxidation differs by more than 100 mV, which manifests in an offset of the HOMO levels listed in Table 1. The lowest electrochemical band gap was found for caffeine at 2.16 eV, followed by theophylline at 2.24 eV, and the largest band gap of 2.40 eV for theobromine. The significantly larger currents observed for the theobromine sample can be attributed to a slightly larger film thickness of the samples used for the CV measurements of theobromine.

TABLE I
ELECTROCHEMICAL BAND GAP CALCULATED FROM THE HOMO AND LUMO LEVELS

Material	HOMO (eV)	LUMO (eV)	Band gap (eV)
Caffeine	-6.11	-3.95	2.16
Theobromine	-6.28	-3.88	2.40
Theophylline	-6.16	-3.92	2.24

The Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the powders of the three investigated alkaloid derivatives were measured to ensure the integrity of the molecules after the purification process and to provide a comprehensive comparison. The FTIR spectra are displayed in Fig. 4. The spectra conform well to those reported for the three materials by Johnson *et al.* [65]. The spectra of theobromine and theophylline show characteristic vibrational bands at around 3000 cm^{-1} that can be assigned to the N-H stretching vibration of the free, non-methylated N-H groups in the molecules. For theophylline these vibrations appear as a broad band from 3050-2400 cm^{-1} , typical for the imidazole N-H moiety [66], while theobromine shows two broad bands at 3150 cm^{-1} and 3020 cm^{-1} . For caffeine, these absorption bands are absent and the spectrum only shows the C-H stretching bands of the aromatic C-H (3112 cm^{-1}) and methyl C-H (2953 cm^{-1}), which are observed at similar spectral positions for theobromine and

theophylline, confirming the integrity of the methyl substituent groups. Characteristic differences between the three materials can also be observed in the carbonyl stretching vibration region.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of the powders of the three alkaloids, two times purified by vacuum sublimation with labeling of the wavenumbers of selected peaks.

Caffeine and theophylline show a similar C=O stretching band pattern with a weaker band at higher energy of 1696 cm^{-1} and 1701 cm^{-1} , respectively, and a more intense absorption band at lower energy, 1645 cm^{-1} and 1662 cm^{-1} for caffeine and theophylline, respectively. Theobromine on the other hand shows a broad, merged band with two peaks at 1685 cm^{-1} and 1660 cm^{-1} . This difference can be attributed to interaction and hydrogen bonding with the non-methylated N-H group [67].

Impedance spectroscopy is a very useful tool in explaining the processes that occur at interfaces between two dissimilar layers of materials that lead to changes in physical properties of the system; it helps also understanding and quantifying the changes in the electrical properties of the system by studying the effect of polarization on the electrical conductivity modification of the whole system [68], [69], [70]. The impedance spectroscopy analysis of the alkaloid films in metal insulator metal geometry involving bottom and top aluminum electrodes (each 80 nm thick) is presented in Fig. 5, panels (a) and (b). The films of theophylline and theobromine were deposited by physical vapor deposition, with similar thicknesses, at an evaporation rate of 0.1 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$. for theophylline and 0.03 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$. for theobromine in a vacuum of 10^{-6} mbar, whereas the film of caffeine was deposited from a 5 mg/ml solution in chloroform by doctor blading at a speed of 2.5 mm/sec. As can be seen from both panels of the Fig. 5, the three alkaloids show robust dielectric properties, substantiated by (i) a uniform capacitance, with moderate increase (a mere factor of

2-2.5) in its absolute value at low (mHz) frequencies as compared to the high (kHz) frequencies; and (ii) an uniform loss angle that shows no relaxation over a 7 orders of magnitude frequency window, from 10 kHz to 1 mHz. The panels (c) and (d) of the Fig. 5 show the capacitances and the loss angle of the three alkaloids deposited on aluminum bottom electrode that has ~ 33 nm thick electrochemically grown aluminum oxide as its top layer. The respective devices were terminated with top aluminum electrodes. The two investigations presented in the panels (a-b) and (c-d) of Fig. 5 are complementary to one another and substantiate the fact that the working devices with caffeine have on one hand inherently a lower thickness (obvious through the recording of higher capacitance values), and on the other hand contain a limited number of mobile ions, probably due to the presence of remnant solvent in the deposited film, authenticated by a relaxation (dome shape) of the low angle curves.

Fig. 5. Dielectric spectroscopy displaying: a) Capacitance measurement and b) Loss angle, of the alkaloids in metal-insulator-metal structures with the dielectric sandwiched between top and bottom aluminum electrodes. c) Capacitance and d) Loss angle of the alkaloids deposited on ~ 33 nm thick electrochemically grown aluminum oxide with aluminum top electrode.

Fig. 6. Breakdown field measurements expressed in current density vs. applied voltage of the three alkaloids in metal-insulator-metal structure between aluminum bottom and top electrodes. The voltage that caused an irremediable damage to the dielectric is presented in the graph as inset for each of the three alkaloids.

Despite the obvious difficulties to deposit films of controllable surface roughness, we managed to establish several pools of alkaloids in MIM configuration, with constant thicknesses in each pool of fabricated devices. In a similar way to our previous work [71], [72], [73] we extracted the dielectric constant of 3.9 ± 0.1 for caffeine, 3.15 ± 0.1 for theobromine and 3.35 ± 0.2 for theophylline. We investigated also the three alkaloids in MIM configuration with gold bottom and top electrodes. However, in this configuration we could not obtain dielectric behavior for theobromine, but only for caffeine and theophylline (see Fig. 3S). The fact that theobromine does not show dielectric properties when grown directly on gold (see SI file, Fig. 4S) is possibly due to the fact that gold is a metal which normally requires the presence of a self-assembled silane monolayer in order to assist the growth of organic molecules [74]. Theophylline and caffeine on the other hand have good dielectric properties even when grown on gold electrode (see the SI file, Fig. 3S, where theobromine is shown for comparison, sandwiched between aluminum bottom and top electrodes). An example of the breakdown field measurement is shown in Fig. 6, where the current density is plotted versus the applied voltage of the gate electrode, in a similar fashion

Fig. 7. Contact angle with water droplet of the investigated alkaloids: a) caffeine; b) theobromine; c) theophylline. The white artifacts displayed as squares inside the images a) and c) are simply caused by the light reflection on the water droplet, and have no scientific value

reported elsewhere [75], [76]. In Fig. 6 all the alkaloid films were sandwiched between aluminum electrodes, being in fact the MIM structures on the devices with C_{60} semiconductor grown on the alkaloids deposited on the plain aluminum gate electrodes for the OFETs transfer characteristics recording (Fig. 13 in the text). The breakdown field measured for the three alkaloids was ~ 1.4 MV/cm for caffeine, 2.15 MV/cm for theobromine and 2.2 MV/cm for theophylline, and the measured film thicknesses by profilometry was 70 nm for caffeine, 65 nm for theophylline and 72 nm for theobromine, since our intention was to deposit similar film thicknesses in order to establish a good comparison between the three materials. The area of the MIM structure was 0.8 mm^2 , offered by the mask design with 2 mm wide gate electrode and 0.4 mm wide top metal electrode (see Fig. 2S in the supplementary information file). The voltages that caused the irremediable damage to the dielectric are displayed as insets on the graph and are far beyond the window of operation for the three materials presented in Fig. 13 that did not exceed 3 V applied gate voltage.

However, the breakdown field values as well as the above reported dielectric constants of these materials should be considered with caution, given their high tendency for crystallization and the subsequent nonuniform surfaces, a topic that will be further elaborated in this article. With this respect

we speculate that a much-optimized growth method of the alkaloid films would make possible the recording of higher values for the breakdown field of the three alkaloids comprised in this study. In addition, a systematic study that takes into account the thickness variation of the three alkaloid films may

Fig. 8. Topography and CPD images ($15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$) of alkaloid films on 100 nm thick Cr/Au electrode on glass substrate: (a) topography of ~ 100 nm thick caffeine film solution deposited by blade coating, (b) corresponding CPD image of the caffeine film, (c) topography of ~ 100 nm vacuum deposited theobromine film, (d) corresponding CPD of the theobromine film, (e) topography of ~ 100 nm vacuum deposited theophylline film, (f) corresponding CPD of the theophylline film.

These particles have an equivalent disc radius range of 100-300 nm and a height range of 300-500 nm, with an average rms roughness of ~ 67.1 nm for a $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ selected area containing uniform distribution of large particles. The reason for choosing $15 \mu\text{m}$ as the scanning size is because there are more large sized particles randomly scattering on the larger $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}^2$ surface (2-3 μm in height), which makes it impossible to have the AM-KPFM scan without the tip contacting the sample on the second pass (see Fig. 1S of the SI file). The corresponding CPD image (Fig. 8 (b)) demonstrates a strong correlation with the topography image (*i.e.* CPD roughness, ~ 42.4 mV), suggesting the presence of two distinct materials within the large particles and the base coating. Nevertheless, by comparing the deviations in height and potential of the particles, it can be confirmed that the two materials composing the particles with different sizes and heights belong in fact to the same material as the base, caffeine.

provide a full picture (Weibull distribution) of the dielectric breakdown strength of these molecules [77].

The contact angle with water droplet of the alkaloids reveals the presence of hydrophilic surfaces for all the materials investigated, with caffeine being the least and theophylline the most hydrophilic in the group (Fig. 7). The respective values of the contact angle were 38.68° for theophylline, 48.10° for theobromine and 70.62° for caffeine. The contact angle of the dielectric films is a critical piece of information to obtain in order to interface the respective dielectric with hydrogen bonded semiconductors [78]. However, the values of the contact angle for the three alkaloid films prove that the respective films have a rather hydrophilic surface that cannot afford the growth of hydrogen bonded semiconductors like indigo, Tyrian purple, epindolidione or quinacridone to name a few [24]. Fig. 8 presents the typical topography and CPD images of all three alkaloid films, caffeine, theobromine and theophylline, all approximately 100 nm thick, deposited on Cr/Au layer on glass. The thickness of the Cr/Au layer was 100 nm in total, of which 10 nm Cr and 90 nm Au, deposited in a physical vapor deposition system inside a glove box. The differences between the three alkaloid materials revealed by Fig. 8 are significant. The topography analysis of the caffeine film in Fig. 8 (a) reveals the random scattering of large particles across the surface.

Moving on to the theobromine film, its topography, Fig. 8 (c) illustrates also a random distribution of particles on the surface. The particles have an equivalent disc radius range of less than 100 nm and a height range of 60-110 nm. The corresponding CPD image, Fig. 8 (d) shows weaker fluctuations compared to caffeine and exhibits a weak correlation with the topography image, indicating no obvious segregation during the growth of the theobromine film. Lastly, the topography of the theophylline film, Fig. 8 (e) reveals two types of particles (A and B). Particle type A has an equivalent disc radius range of 100-500 nm and a height range of over 100 nm, while particle type B has an equivalent disc radius range of 20-200 nm and a height range of 50-80 nm (the two types of particles are uniformly distributed on every surface we scanned, as one can see the SI file, Fig. 5S). The CPD image shown in Fig. 8 (f) exhibits a strong correlation with the topography image. Importantly, the contact potential of particle type A differs from that of particle type B ($CPA > CPB$), indicating the presence of two distinct materials within particles A and B.

The topography and CPD of the three alkaloid films grown on plain aluminum electrode of 100 nm thickness on glass substrate (Fig. 9) reproduces closely the results obtained for the respective organic materials grown on chromium-gold electrode.

Fig. 9. Topography and CPD images ($15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$) of alkaloid films on 100 nm thick plain aluminum electrode on glass substrate: a) topography of ~ 100 nm thick caffeine film solution deposited by blade coating, b) corresponding CPD image of the caffeine film, c) topography of ~ 100 nm vacuum deposited theobromine film, d) corresponding CPD of the theobromine film, e) topography of ~ 100 nm vacuum deposited theophylline film, f) corresponding CPD of the theophylline film.

The caffeine film shows two distinct growth models with columnar features randomly peppered over a surface of more uniform base film. The height roughness (rms) of the caffeine films is $\sim 56.2 \pm 3.8$ nm, and the contact potential difference (CPD) of 4.7 ± 1.8 mV. In a similar fashion to the theobromine grown on chromium-gold, also the theobromine grown on plain aluminum shows weaker fluctuations compared to caffeine and displays a weak correlation with the topography image, both facts indicating no obvious segregation during the growth of the theobromine film. The height roughness of theobromine film (rms) was measured to be $\sim 69.9 \pm 2.3$ nm and the contact potential difference (CPD) of 5.4 ± 0.9 mV. Lastly, the topography of the theophylline film deposited on plain aluminum electrode shows a more uniform pattern composed

of one type of particle only compared to the counterpart grown on chromium-gold electrode. The height roughness of theophylline film (rms) was the highest among the three materials investigated, measuring $\sim 158.5 \pm 9.3$ nm and the contact potential difference (CPD) of 40.8 ± 3.0 mV. All the three alkaloid materials have a high tendency towards crystallization, creating a relatively smooth surface that is uniformly sprayed with large columnar aggregates as it is obvious in the case of caffeine. Theobromine and theophylline behave in a similar way, albeit not to the extent shown by caffeine. However, considering a $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ area for caffeine, theobromine and theophylline with uniform distribution of large aggregates, the RMS of topography roughness of caffeine, theobromine and theophylline films surface are 67.1 nm, 22.6 nm and 28.8 nm, respectively when grown on chromium-gold electrodes and 56.2 nm, 69.9 nm and 158.5 nm respectively when grown on plain aluminum electrode.

On both electrodes the caffeine sample contains both the largest and the highest sized particles on the surface, resulting in the largest RMS value compared to the other two alkaloids. Nevertheless, it is fair to point out that the caffeine film displays also the smoothest base surface, as Fig. 1S demonstrates (*i.e.* in a carefully selected $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ area, without the presence of any large aggregate particle, the rms roughness of the caffeine base film is ~ 3.5 nm and its corresponding CPD roughness is 14.4 mV). The RMS of CPD fluctuations within caffeine, theobromine, theophylline samples are 42.4 mV, 11.3 mV and 20.6 mV respectively when grown on chromium-gold electrodes and 4.7 mV, 5.4 mV and 40.8 mV respectively when grown on aluminum electrodes, considering areas with uniform distribution of large aggregate particles. Comparatively, the RMS values of CPD fluctuations within clean SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 are 17.4 mV and 82.0 mV, respectively, measured on fresh samples in our laboratory. The surfaces of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 are about two orders of magnitude smoother than those of the alkaloid samples, with a surface roughness rms of 0.1 nm and 0.8 nm respectively, also measured in our laboratory. The surface roughness and contact potential difference of the three alkaloid films are summarized in Table II.

The topography of the two semiconductors, pentacene and C_{60} grown on the three alkaloid samples is presented in Fig. 10. The morphology of the pentacene and C_{60} differs significantly, and interestingly, some of the high particles from the underneath alkaloid films still can be seen after pentacene or C_{60} growth. Both semiconductor grains are uniform in size, but pentacene grows in aggregates of grains of typical size of 200 to 300 nm, whereas the grains of C_{60} are very small, in the range of ~ 20 nm. The initial roughness of the alkaloid films is further projected to the surface of the two semiconductors, and the calculated rms roughness are 10.9 nm, 22.4 nm, 24.3 nm, 17.8 nm, 51.2 nm, and 19.4 nm, for the materials shown sequentially in Fig. 10 (a) to Fig. 10 (f) respectively. The OFETs geometry

utilized in this work involved a staggered bottom gate-top contact (BG-TC) structure on glass substrates. Fig. 2S in the SI file shows the masks used in the fabrication sequence. The OFET devices with pentacene (p-type semiconductor) and C₆₀ (n-type semiconductor) with each of the three alkaloids discussed in this work as gate dielectrics on plain (not anodized) aluminum gate are presented in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 respectively. As discussed in the previous sections of the article, and detailed in the experimental section, the caffeine layer was the only one not deposited by vacuum processing, but rather by blade coating a caffeine solution in chloroform under ambient conditions. We investigated with this respect various concentrations of caffeine spanning from 2 mg/ml to 100 mg/ml, and found that the best film forming for OFETs fabrication perspective is offered by the solution of caffeine

having 5 mg/ml concentration. Lower concentration solutions of caffeine produced films of caffeine too thin to work independently as dielectric layer, whereas the higher concentration solution produced films of increased surface roughness, given the extreme tendency of caffeine to crystallize and the fast (uncontrollable) evaporation of chloroform in ambient conditions under which the blade-coating step was performed. We investigated of course also caffeine deposited by vacuum sublimation, but irrespective of the evaporation rate, the films turn out to be of impractical surface roughness for electronics fabrication.

TABLE II
THE RMS SURFACE ROUGHNESS AND RMS CONTACT POTENTIAL DIFFERENCE OF THE ALKALOID FILMS

Alkaloid	RMS surface roughness (nm)		RMS contact potential difference (mV)	
	Cr/Au electrode	Al electrode	Cr/Au electrode	Al electrode
Caffeine	67.1	56.2	42.4	4.7
Theobromine	22.6	69.9	11.3	5.4
Theophylline	28.8	158.5	20.6	40.8

Interestingly, we observed that caffeine sublimates spontaneously (albeit very slowly), without any heating necessary under the typical pressure of evaporation of 10⁻⁶ mbar that our instrument (Edwards High Vacuum) reaches. This event was not observable for theobromine and theophylline, and together with the inferior quality of caffeine films obtained by vacuum processing, prompted us to find alternative routes of film formation, such as blade coating or spin coating. Between the latter two, the blade coating proved the most beneficial, since spin coating caffeine from chloroform rendered nonuniform films because of the uncontrollable evaporation of the solvent and the high tendency of caffeine for crystallization. For the vacuum processible films of theobromine and theophylline, we investigated several deposition rates from very slow (0.01 Å/sec.) to very fast (10 Å/sec.), and observed that a slow rate offers a good compromise between a film having a good dielectric behavior and a smooth enough film, yet compact that can be employed as dielectric layer in OFETs. Different than our past work dealing with natural dielectrics [71], [72], [73], in this work we performed a systematic study of fabricating devices both on plain aluminum and plain gold gate electrodes (*i.e.* both unpassivated) as well as on top of the electrochemically grown aluminum oxide, where the three alkaloids act as a capping layer, or in other words as passivating layer.

Nevertheless, it has to be acknowledged that a ultra-thin, yet not defect-free [79], [80], [81], [82] aluminum oxide film dielectric [75] does exist on the top surface of the aluminum gate [59], due to the unavoidable exposure to ambient oxygen during handling of the glass slide in laboratory throughout the fabrication protocol. In spite of the known high resistivity of the aluminum oxide, the natural oxide of aluminum is not useful as a stand-alone insulating film and electrons tunnel it easily [83]. This ~ 1-1.5 nm thick film of aluminum oxide spontaneously formed during the exposure of the aluminum surface with ambient air is only dense enough to account for corrosion protection and to prevent redox reactions in air. However, the natural oxide of aluminum has no actual applications for electronics, and thus is not feasible for being employed as stand-alone dielectric in OFETs.

The films of the alkaloids deposited on plain aluminum gate for the OFET devices presented in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 were in the range of 60 to 70 nm in thickness for theobromine and theophylline and about 60 nm for the solution processed caffeine. The specific capacitances (*i.e.* capacitance density, denoted as C_{0d} in this work) of the OFETs were measured on the MIM structure situated at the bottom of the glass slide hosting the 4 OFET devices on each slide, a geometry employed in all our previous publications^{52,71,72,73,84}. The values of specific capacitances (C_{0d}) were extracted from the impedance spectrum at 1 kHz frequency. The variation in thickness of the vacuum

deposited films of theobromine and theophylline was due to the position of the slides onto the sample holder, that received slightly different amount of vacuum sublimed materials from the centrally positioned crucible situated at a distance of 20 cm below.

Fig. 10 Atomic force microscopy scans on the top of 60 nm thick organic semiconductors pentacene and C_{60} : a) pentacene grown on caffeine, surface roughness, rms ~ 10.9 nm; b) C_{60} grown on caffeine, surface roughness, rms ~ 22.4 nm; c) pentacene grown on theobromine, surface roughness, rms ~ 24.3 nm; d) C_{60} grown on theobromine, surface roughness rms ~ 17.8 nm; e) pentacene grown on theophylline, surface roughness, rms ~ 51.2 nm; f) C_{60} grown on theophylline, surface roughness, rms ~ 19.4 nm

In a separate study, we wanted to understand whether the three alkaloids work independently as dielectric layers on a metal gate that does not form an insulating oxide layer, such as gold. While the respective OFET devices worked decently for the alkaloids deposited directly on the gold gate (see Fig. 13 displaying only the transfer characteristics), they presented a more pronounced leakage current in the transfer characteristics than the devices presented in this study fabricated on plain aluminum gate that has inherently a layer of metal oxide of ~ 1 - 1.5 nm in thickness on its surface. It seems therefore plausible to conclude that even though not being a defect-free layer, the thin, native, aluminum oxide still helps in the final outcome of the OFET performance and complements well the organic dielectric insulating capability. On the other hand, one cannot rule out the different growth mechanism of the organic materials on aluminum versus gold surfaces. The poor performance of the devices of theobromine deposited on gold

shown in Fig. 13 panels (c) and (d) (in honesty these two represent the only OFET devices that somehow worked) substantiate nicely the observed results of the respective organic material deposited in metal-insulator-metal configuration between gold electrodes for impedance measurement (Fig. 4S). With this respect a more focused study involving absorption-desorption spectroscopy and surface transmission microscopy and grazing angle XRD measurements will definitely shed more light into this issue.

The devices with pentacene and C_{60} grown on the three alkaloids (~ 50 - 70 nm thick, depending on the sample position in the holder) acting this time as capping layer for the electrochemically grown aluminum oxide (~ 33 nm thick) are presented in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 respectively. The alumina layer was grown electrochemically through via a method reported elsewhere [85] and well established in our laboratory [59], [73]. We employed for this study an anodization voltage (*i.e.* 20 V) that produced a film of alumina ~ 32 nm thickness. The total thickness of the alumina was ~ 33 nm if one considers also the native oxide layer formed spontaneously during the exposure of the aluminum gate electrode to the ambient air. The comparison between the performance of the alkaloid films as stand-alone dielectrics (Fig. 11, Fig. 12 and Fig. 13) and as inorganic dielectric capping layers (Fig. 14 and Fig. 15) can be made by inspecting the figure of merit of the respective OFETs, presented in Table III. In Table III, the statistical deviation of the specific capacitances is presented, comprising the entire pool of the “working” fabricated devices considered for this study. The respective values of the field effect mobility displayed in Table III can be adjusted considering similar standard deviation brackets as for the specific capacitances, since the two are mathematically related [86].

Although the differences in the field effect mobility values are not significant, they show favorable application of these molecules as dielectric capping layer and even stand-alone dielectric towards pentacene rather than C_{60} . Similarly, all the OFET devices displayed an ON-OFF ratio in excess of 10^4 when alkaloids were interfaced with pentacene, but slightly lower values for C_{60} . Obviously, the subthreshold swing values were much smaller for the OFETs with stand-alone alkaloid dielectrics, mainly due to the lower window of operating voltage. However, comparing the Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 on one side with the respective counterpart Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, one can clearly see that the presence of aluminum oxide helps the OFET devices display a much lower leakage current all throughout the operation window. With this respect, the I_{gs} current of all the devices with the three alkaloids employed as capping layer for alumina inorganic dielectric is situated in the range of tens to hundred picoamperes (Fig. 14 and Fig. 15), basically one order of magnitude or more below the respective level of the leakage current recorded on stand-alone organic alkaloids as dielectric (*i.e.* Fig. 11 and Fig. 12). Also, as a general trend, the devices with fullerene, C_{60} , display a slightly higher hysteresis when compared with the counterpart devices with pentacene as organic semiconductor. Theophylline on the other hand seems to be the one material that generates higher hysteresis in OFET characteristics compared to the other two alkaloids, whereas caffeine shows the best performance in the studied group in terms of hysteresis, especially when interfaced with pentacene. It is interesting to observe that despite its high tendency towards

crystallization, caffeine offers the best performance in OFETs for both semiconductors; the field effect mobilities surpass $0.1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ with ON/OFF ratio in excess of 10^4 and the subthreshold swing among the best devices in the entire pool reported here. It is also fair to report that the success rate (reproducibility) of devices with caffeine as stand-alone dielectric was centered around a modest $\sim 40\%$, far more inferior than the one of theobromine and theophylline that both scored in the 80% range when employed as stand-alone dielectrics on plain aluminum gate. The unreliable devices displayed either high leakage or low on-off ratio, or both, probably due to the unfavorable growth of the organic semiconductors on the rough surface of the alkaloid dielectrics. Nevertheless, the devices that worked were all similar to the ones depicted in the Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. It is interesting to note also that the statistics provided by KPFM and AFM measurements do not directly translate into the expected performance of the respective dielectrics in OFETs. With this respect, averagely rough surfaces like caffeine, have regions with acceptable smoothness as described in the text here, while also the growth of an organic layer is very much influenced by the inorganic substrate underneath, like for example theobromine. In our previous work we showed that the OFET performance is not directly influenced by the average surface roughness (see Ref. [87]), where devices built on rougher surfaces like cytosine and thymine were superior to those fabricated on guanine. As a matter of fact, in the respective study, the best film forming dielectric material, *i.e.* guanine, produced modest performance OFETs in terms of ON-OFF ratio, hysteresis, and field effect mobility. In the present study it is rather difficult to assess unequivocally whether the surface roughness of the dielectric and its interface towards the pentacene or C_{60} semiconductors is responsible for the recorded lower mobility values (especially for theophylline, a fact observed for other dielectric-semiconductor systems in the literature, with pentacene as a prime example of a semiconductor whose performance is severely affected by the quality of the dielectric interface^{88,89,90}), or is the reactivity (*i.e.* chemical interaction) between the dielectric and the semiconductor, in line with our previous finding on guanine [Ref. 87].

On the other hand, the reproducibility of devices when the three alkaloids were employed as dielectric capping layer on the electrochemically grown alumina (in the pool of devices comprising Fig. 14 and Fig. 15) was very good for all three alkaloids. However, a direct consequence of the presence of the aluminum oxide is the increased thickness of the dielectric layer that requires a higher effective voltage in order to generate the necessary charges required to operate the transistor. As a positive event, a direct consequence of the presence of a thicker (inorganic-organic) dielectric is the better insulating properties of the dielectric layer, that reflects itself in a significantly lower leakage current (I_{gs}) for all the devices fabricated. Table III displays also the normalized subthreshold swing values for the dielectrics employed in this study, S_n , which is a product of the

subthreshold swing, S_{sw} , and the specific capacitance, C_{od} [Ref. 86]. The normalized subthreshold swing gives the necessary number of gate-induced carriers to generate a one-decade increase in the current near V_0 and is therefore a meaningful comparison of semiconductor films grown on different dielectrics [86]. The comparison of the S_n values between devices fabricated in similar conditions (*i.e.* directly on aluminum gates and on top of aluminum oxides respectively) shows that the normalized subthreshold swing is higher for the devices fabricated on aluminum oxide, given the higher subthreshold swing and their higher operating voltage. However, when deposited directly on aluminum gate electrodes, the three alkaloids display comparable values of the S_n , with a slight advantage for caffeine and theobromine, given their lower operating voltage and higher recorded mobility values than the respective values for theophylline.

Fig. 11. OFETs with pentacene and the investigated alkaloids deposited on plain aluminum gate: a)-b) Transfer and Output characteristic .respectively of pentacene on caffeine dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 85.5$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.35$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 98$ mV/dec.; c)-d) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of pentacene on theobromine dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 71.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.23$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 81$ mV/dec.; e)-f) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of pentacene on theophylline dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 74.5$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.081$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 152$ mV/dec.

Fig. 12. OFETs with C₆₀ semiconductor on the investigated alkaloids on plain aluminum gate: a)-b) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of C₆₀ on caffeine dielectric, specific capacitance C_{0d} = 86.2 nF/cm², field effect mobility μ = 0.32 cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing S_{sw} = 170 mV/dec.; c)-d) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of C₆₀ on theobromine dielectric, specific capacitance C_{0d} = 71.2 nF/cm², field effect mobility μ = 0.012 cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing S_{sw} = 387 mV/dec.; e)-h) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of C₆₀ on theophylline dielectric, specific capacitance C_{0d} = 80.1 nF/cm², field effect mobility μ = 0.04 cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing S_{sw} = 300 mV/dec.

Fig. 13. Transfer characteristics of caffeine, theobromine and theophylline as dielectrics on plain gold gate electrodes. (a) caffeine with pentacene semiconductor; (b) caffeine with C₆₀ semiconductor; (c) theobromine with pentacene semiconductor; (d) theobromine with C₆₀ semiconductor; (e) theophylline with pentacene semiconductor; (f) theophylline with C₆₀ semiconductor.

Table III

PARAMETERS OF THE FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTORS WITH C₆₀ AND PENTACENE DEPOSITED ON CAFFEINE, THEOBROMINE AND THEOPHYLLINE DIELECTRICS, ON PLAIN AL GATE ELECTRODES AND ALUMINUM OXIDE RESPECTIVELY

Alkaloid	Substrate	OFET parameters											
		with Pentacene						with C ₆₀					
		V _{th} (V)	I _{ON} /I _{OFF}	μ (cm ² /Vs)	C _{0d} (nF/cm ²)	S _{sw} (mV/dec.)	Sn (VnF/cm ² dec.)	V _{th} (V)	I _{ON} /I _{OFF}	μ (cm ² /Vs)	C _{0d} (nF/cm ²)	S _{sw} (mV/dec.)	Sn (VnF/cm ² dec.)
Caffeine	plain aluminum	-0.8	3×10 ⁴	0.11	85.5±4.3	98	8379	0.35	1×10 ⁴	0.1	86.2±5.1	170	14654
	aluminum oxide	-0.5	1.5×10 ⁴	0.016	66.1±2.5	850	56185	1.6	467	0.027	64.4±3.7	1900	122360
Theobromine	plain aluminum	-0.9	9×10 ⁴	0.054	71.1±2.5	81	5759	0.6	576	0.025	71.2±3.3	387	27554
	aluminum oxide	-0.5	4.1×10 ⁴	0.012	56.9±1.8	480	27312	4.5	2.8×10 ³	0.1	57.1±2.1	1400	79940
Theophylline	plain aluminum	-1.1	1×10 ⁴	0.018	74.5±3.7	152	11324	0.3	2×10 ³	0.015	80.1±3.8	300	24030
	aluminum oxide	-1	1.3×10 ⁵	0.06	58.5±1.6	198	11583	3.9	6×10 ⁴	0.05	59.5±2.0	1100	65450

Fig. 14. OFETs with pentacene and the investigated alkaloids deposited on 33 nm thick aluminum oxide gate dielectric: a)-b) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of pentacene on caffeine dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 66.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.016$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 850$ mV/dec.; c)-d) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of pentacene on theobromine dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 56.9$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.012$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 480$ mV/dec.; e)-f) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of pentacene on theophylline dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 58.5$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.06$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 198$ mV/dec.

Fig. 15. OFETs with C_{60} semiconductor on the investigated alkaloids deposited on 33 nm aluminum oxide gate dielectric: a)-b) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of C_{60} on caffeine dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 64.4$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.027$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 1.9$ V/dec.; c)-d) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of C_{60} on theobromine dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 57.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.1$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 1.4$ V/dec.; e)-h) Transfer and Output characteristic respectively of C_{60} on theophylline dielectric, specific capacitance $C_{0d} = 59.5$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 0.05$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 1.1$ V/dec.

As demonstrated by the AM-KPFM investigation, even though caffeine has the highest tendency for crystallization, its columnar structure is randomly scattered on the surface, and one can identify areas of $15 \mu\text{m}^2$ that have a rms roughness of $\sim 3 \text{ nm}$, ideal for the growth of an organic semiconductor (see Fig. 1S in the SI file). Caffeine OFET devices work at $\pm 1.5\text{-}2 \text{ V}$ operating gate voltage and display a good transfer characteristic even when operated with $\pm 10 \text{ mV}$ drain-source voltage, which we find remarkable. Theobromine and theophylline showed similarly good performances when interfaced with pentacene, with operating voltages, V_{gs} of -2 V for theobromine and -4 V for theophylline and the lowest source-drain voltages of -10 mV and -20 mV respectively. However, the corresponding devices interfaced with C_{60} showed more modest performance as compared to caffeine- C_{60} dielectric-semiconductor couple; the lowest source-drain voltages that could raise the transfer characteristic were -100 mV for theobromine and -500 mV for theophylline. In the Fig. 11 and the Fig. 12, the transfer curves for the lowest source-drain voltages that could raise a transfer characteristic are displayed in red type. Interestingly, also for the fullerene based OFETs, the off-current in the transfer characteristics is significantly higher for the case of alkaloids used as interfacial layer on top of the aluminum oxide than when deposited directly on aluminum gate, (see Fig. 12 and 15). A possible explanation may be the interaction of the alkaloids (especially caffeine and theobromine) with the aluminum oxide that gives rise to an interface between the two materials that is electron rich and contributes to a higher plateau of the I_{ds} current when the transistor is in the off state.

Furthermore, we measured the device with C_{60} shown in Fig. 12 (a) also with 0 V (zero volt) drain-source voltage and we obtained a transfer characteristic, albeit with very low I_{ds} current of barely 0.1 nA (see Fig. 6S). This charge transport in the channel at zero applied V_{ds} voltage cannot be due to other factors than to the drift of charges. We raised this characteristic when measuring the device with 1 mV increment and 1 second delay between measurement points, but could not obtain this transfer characteristic at 2 mV increment for example. We want to point out that this behavior was singular to caffeine- C_{60} device in this study, and was not observed for any other combination of alkaloids-semiconductors, not even for caffeine-pentacene. The lowest operating voltage window that we could measure for the alkaloids based OFETs was for an exceptional (albeit singular) device with caffeine, blade coated at 2.5 mm/sec blade speed from a 2 mg/ml solution in chloroform (SI file, Fig. 7S) on plain aluminum electrode. The respective device worked at 400 mV gate voltage and had a measured field effect mobility of $0.025 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ for a specific capacitance of 513 nF/cm^2 of the caffeine dielectric. Likewise, the higher operating voltage that we measured in our laboratory on any alkaloid system involved theobromine deposited at a

very slow rate, *i.e.* 0.01 A/sec. , in a $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ thick dielectric layer on plain aluminum electrode (no externally induced aluminum oxide, other than by spontaneous oxidation of the top layer in ambient oxygen). The respective device with C_{60} as organic semiconductor is presented in Fig. 8S in the SI file, and worked at the maximum gate and drain voltages possible to measure on our instrument, *i.e.* 190 V , and 100 V respectively. The measured specific capacitance of the respective theobromine layer was 3 nF/cm^2 , and the calculated field effect mobility, $1.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. The device displays a very large clockwise hysteresis, due to the very high surface roughness of the dielectric [56], [73], [91], induced by the growth of C_{60} on an unusually thick and also rough dielectric layer [92], [93]. The reason for showing this “underperforming” device is to draw attention to the quality of the dielectric layer in terms of leakage current at the maximum operating gate and drain voltages. This leakage current is no more than 200 pA , and in agreement with the impedance spectroscopy investigations demonstrate the good performance of the theobromine as dielectric. The devices where the alkaloids were employed as capping layer for the electrochemically grown aluminum oxide, presented in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, all operate at a comparable voltage window of $\sim 7\text{-}10 \text{ volts}$ and display similar performance to one another, demonstrating that the role of the main dielectric in this case rests on the aluminum oxide.

We further investigated the performance of OFETs having the pentacene and C_{60} deposited directly on unpassivated aluminum oxide layer, in order to see whether the alkaloids layers are necessary or not. The respective aluminum oxide of $\sim 11 \text{ nm}$ in thickness was formed by anodization (*i.e.* by applying 8 V anodization voltage) via a method reported elsewhere and well established in our laboratory [85]. We also looked here into two avenues: 1) using the aluminum oxide samples coming immediately after the electrochemical step, where the anodized gate electrode was only washed copiously with ultrapure water and, 2) using samples that were electrochemically anodized and had a supplementary step of cleaning via oxygen plasma for 2 minutes at 98 W of the power of the plasma, in order to cleave away any remnant physisorbed citric acid residue that was resistant to removal by washing with deionized water. We employed for this purpose an anodization voltage of 8 V for aluminum that gave rise to a layer of aluminum of total thickness of $\sim 11 \text{ nm}$, including here the layer of native oxide formed spontaneously in air. As a rule of thumb, the working voltage on the probe station (*i.e.* the maximum V_{gs} endured without breaking the dielectric), of an OFET anodized electrochemically is about half of the anodization voltage imposed during anodization process. That mean that we expected our devices (*i.e.* C_{60} and pentacene deposited directly on $\sim 11 \text{ nm}$ aluminum oxide, without any passivation layer) to work without significant leakage at $\sim 3\text{V}$ operating voltage

which was indeed the case, as the devices in Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 show for both the transfer and the output characteristics. The main reason for choosing 8 V anodization voltage was to generate OEFT devices working in a similar voltage operational window as the ones presented in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 are very interesting to examine and analyze in conjunction with Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 for example. Pentacene is definitely much less influenced than C_{60} by the unpassivated inorganic dielectric, at least in the physical appearance of the characteristics (see Fig. 16 and Fig. 17), *i.e.* in terms of maximum I_{ds} level obtained by the OFET devices and no visible hysteresis. However, a closer look reveals that in the OFETs with pentacene reaching a similar I_{ds} currents (*i.e.* $\sim 1 \mu A$ at 3 V operating voltage, see the graphs in Fig. 11), for the AlOx passivated with a capping layer (here we refer to the alkaloids, but the observation is general anyway), the OFF level is between one to two orders of magnitude lower, and the field effect mobility also higher than for the case of unpassivated AlOx. However, in the case of C_{60} , the passivation of the inorganic layer is definitely needed (see the transfer characteristics shown in Fig. 16 (c-d)). Also, it seems plausible to infer that an absolutely clean surface of the inorganic dielectric (*i.e.* as it is the one obtained after the oxygen plasma step when any remnant physically bound adsorbed layer of citric acid is removed), is far more reactive than a surface of the metal oxide utilized immediately after the electrochemical layer growth. This extreme reactivity of an absolutely pure aluminum oxide surface is supported by the evidence of the exorbitantly large hysteresis, and low field effect mobility, in the range of $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ (see Fig. 16 (d)). The red lines in Fig. 16 (a) and Fig. 16 (c) are inserted only for an easy visualization of the importance of passivation process for aluminum oxide; the respective red curves represent OFETs belonging to the same fabrication batch of aluminum gates as for the Al gates that

underwent electrochemical oxidation, but this time deposited with theobromine and theophylline respectively directly on the aluminum gate (or on the thin native aluminum oxide formed by spontaneous oxidation in air). The red curve in Fig. 16 (c) is actually the theophylline OFET displayed in Fig. 12 (e), while the red curve in Fig. 16 (a) is an OFET with theobromine on plain Al gate working at 3 V operating gate voltage. Fig. 17 presents the output characteristics of the devices displayed in Fig. 16 as black lines in their transfer characteristics. The observations stemming from the output curves of Fig. 17 are complementary to those pertaining to the transfer characteristics of Fig. 16: pentacene is relatively insensitive to the reactivity of the unpassivated inorganic layer, whereas C_{60} behaves exactly in antithesis to pentacene. The devices with the inorganic layer resulted after the anodization step (having presumably a physisorbed layer of remnant citric acid, despite our vigorous washing step with ultrapure 18 M Ω water) behave quite decently, at a first glance. Nevertheless, a pitching down of the saturation curves is visible, characteristic to a significant deep state trapping at the surface of the inorganic dielectric to the organic semiconductor. The device with C_{60} deposited on an ultrapure inorganic dielectric (Fig. 17 (c-d)) is an example of the transistor behavior when fullerene is deposited on unpassivated inorganic dielectric surfaces⁹⁴. The respective OFET opens late (*i.e.* only three V_{gs} curves are visible in the output characteristics), since the threshold voltage is greater than 2 V, visible also in the transfer characteristics of Fig. 17 (d), since the output was measured immediately after the completion of the transfer characteristic. Similar to the case of the inorganic dielectric having presumably only a monolayer of passivator (*i.e.* citric acid in Fig. 16 c)), all the curves pitch down in saturation regime for the OFET with C_{60} deposited on ultra-pure AlOx surface (Fig. 17 (d)).

Fig. 16. Transfer characteristics of pentacene and C_{60} grown on plain $AlOx$, without any capping layer (i.e. unpassivated) shown as black curves: a) pentacene on electrochemically grown $AlOx$; specific capacitance $C_{od} = 938.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 1.6 \times 10^{-2}$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 323$ mV/dec.; b) pentacene on electrochemically grown $AlOx + O_2$ plasma exposure for 10 minutes, at the power of 98 W; specific capacitance $C_{od} = 938.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 2.7 \times 10^{-2}$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 715$ mV/dec.; c) C_{60} on electrochemically grown $AlOx$; specific capacitance $C_{od} = 938.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 9.3 \times 10^{-3}$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 395$ mV/dec.; d) C_{60} on electrochemically grown $AlOx + O_2$ plasma exposure for 10 minutes, at the power of 98 W; specific capacitance $C_{od} = 938.1$ nF/cm², field effect mobility $\mu = 2.6 \times 10^{-4}$ cm²/Vs, subthreshold swing $S_{sw} = 305$ mV/dec. The red curves in the panels a) and c) show devices passivated with theobromine, field effect mobility $\mu = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ cm²/Vs, and theophylline, field effect mobility $\mu = 1.5 \times 10^{-2}$ cm²/Vs respectively.

Fig. 17. Output characteristics of pentacene and C₆₀ grown on plain AlO_x, without any capping layer: a) pentacene on electrochemically grown AlO_x; b) pentacene on electrochemically grown AlO_x + O₂ plasma exposure for 10 minutes, at the power of 98 W; c) C₆₀ on electrochemically grown AlO_x; d) C₆₀ on electrochemically grown AlO_x + O₂ plasma exposure for 10 minutes, at the power of 98 W.

The vacuum processible alkaloids presented in this study compare favorably with other systems reported by our group and deposited by vacuum sublimation, *e.g.* nucleobases (adenine, guanine, thymine and cytosine) [87], [95], polymers (polyaniline, polyethylene) [56], [57], or small molecules (melamine, perylene or anthraquinone derivatives) [56], [58], [94], [96]. With this respect factors like ease of purification via train-sublimation method [52] and low temperature of processing (*i.e.* ~ 80 °C for caffeine, ~ 125 °C for theophylline and ~ 140 °C for theobromine in 1×10^{-6} mbar vacuum for a stable evaporation rate of $0.1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$.) are in the same range to the respective values of many of the vacuum processible materials enumerated above. In addition, caffeine can be processed also from solution. Moreover, the investigated alkaloids have good dielectric properties and afford a high breakdown field, that is remarkable for vacuum sublimed films [87]. Although these three small molecules look alike, as the schematic in Fig. 1 shows, they are rather different and behave differently from one another as their processing conditions demonstrate (evaporation temperature, solubility in classic organic solvents, film forming characteristics, tendency for

crystallization, *etc.*). Ideally these materials should be studied and optimized individually and not as a group. Critically important will be to carefully investigate and optimize the deposition conditions in order to obtain a more controllable and reproducible film growth for all three alkaloids. With this respect, levels of reproducibility that score in the $\sim 40\%$ for the caffeine and $\sim 80\%$ for theobromine and theophylline need significant improvement for further implementation of these dielectrics in industrially relevant developments. After managing to understand and control the growth mechanisms of each individual alkaloid, a systematic study will offer answers to the issues of charge transport and interface trap density at the interface between the alkaloid dielectrics and the organic semiconductors grown on each individual surface. Careful control of threshold voltage values for complementary devices having alkaloids employed as dielectrics with p- and n-type semiconductors will raise the possibility of employing such materials in simple electronic circuits.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we reported organic electronics devices (OFETs) employing three commercially available alkaloids as dielectric layers, caffeine, theobromine and theophylline. We performed a thorough material analysis of these natural molecules and established protocols of thin layer deposition for each of them. These three materials: caffeine, theobromine and theophylline, may look similar to one another as their chemical structure depicted in Fig. 1 suggest, yet they behave differently in their solid-state thin film formation characteristics. An individual fabrication route had to be employed for each alkaloid, with caffeine being the only one recommended for processing from its solution in chloroform. Theobromine and theophylline seem better processible via vapor deposition, yet with a different scheme of evaporation. All three materials have a very strong tendency for crystallization, with caffeine being the most difficult to process. However, these alkaloids have a predisposition to grow in columnar grains uniformly scattered on an area paved by more uniform grains, that helps in obtaining good operating OFET devices, if the source and drain electrodes (the transistor channel and its width) have the chance to fall in the more uniform, smoother area. This was the reason for recording so many failed devices with caffeine, ~ 60%; nevertheless, theobromine and theophylline offered a quite opposite number, *i.e.* ~ 80% working devices. The root-mean-square (rms) of the contact potential for the films of these three materials analyzed by AM-KPFM are in the range of the values obtained for silicon dioxide, but about a factor of 2 to 4 lower than the respective values of aluminum oxide, a material known for having a very reactive surface that needs passivation for proper working as dielectric in OFETs. We demonstrate the validity of these arguments in our transistor data with the three alkaloids deposited directly on aluminum electrode, and also in two parallel studies with the organic semiconductors, C₆₀ and pentacene deposited on electrochemically anodized aluminum with and without the alkaloids as capping layer.

Given their wide availability, and widespread usage in various field, including medicine and food (as dietary components), the three alkaloids investigated here as dielectrics in OFETs can become the materials of choice for applications involving implantable or transient electronics aimed to complement their recording capabilities with providing also a level of therapy. Because of their high tendency for crystallization and difficulties in processing, these molecules definitely need attention from the side of synthetic chemistry community in attaching side chains meant to impart enhanced solubility in benign or even green solvents. With their natural origin, biocompatibility and low toxicity complemented by their robust dielectric properties, these molecules prove themselves as solid candidates for the pool of materials providing sustainability in the field of electronics and dielectric devices.

V. BIOGRAPHY

Cristian Vlad Irimia, is currently pursuing his Master of Science degree in Advanced Materials Science at Graz University of Technology in Graz, Austria. He obtained his Bachelor of Science Degree in Chemistry from the same university in 2024.

He completed six Summer Internships programs in research institutions of Europe on various topics related to bioelectronics:

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In the year 2021, as a twelfth-grader attending the High School in Graz, Austria, Cristian Vlad Irimia was awarded the Bronze Medal in the national contest of the Austrian Chemistry Olympiad. Cristian Vlad Irimia co-authored nine scientific articles of which three were highlighted on the front covers of the publishing journals, and during his short scientific career presented his work at five international conferences.

Cigdem Yumusak is a senior researcher at the Linz Institute for Organic Solar Cells (LIOS) and Institute of Physical Chemistry at the Johannes Kepler University of Linz, Austria.

She completed her BSc., MSc., and Ph.D. degrees in Physics at the Yildiz Technical University, Istanbul, Turkiye.

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Boyuan Ban, photograph and biography not available at the time of publication.

Elisabeth Leeb is a university assistant at Johannes Kepler University in Linz, Austria and is currently working on her PhD thesis in the research group of Prof. Niyazi Serdar Sariciftci at the Institute of Physical Chemistry and Linz Institute for Organic Solar Cells.

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Ms. Leeb's current research interests lie in the field of electrocatalysis, working with bio-derived materials and conductive metal-organic frameworks.

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Andrei Ionut Mardare is a physicist working in the field of thin film combinatorial development of inorganic materials.

He studied Physics at University of Bucharest, Romania and conducted his doctoral work at Max-Planck Institute for Iron Research in Düsseldorf, Germany. He received his Ph.D. degree in Physics in 2009 from Ruhr University Bochum (RUB) Germany, then he joined the

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Christian Teichert, studied Physics at Martin Luther University in Halle, Germany and obtained his Ph.D. in 1992 from the same university. Between 1993 and 1996 he was post-doctoral fellow at the University of Wisconsin Madison, U.S.A, and since 2001 is Associate Professor in Materials Physics, University of Leoben, Austria.

In the year 2002 he was awarded Gaede Prize of the German Vacuum Society and was the recipient of the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation fellowship in the years 1992 and 2014. Between the years 2013 and 2016. Prof. Christian Teichert has been the Chair of the Nanometer Structure Division of the

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Niyazi Serdar Sariciftci is Ordinarius (Chair) Professor at the Institute of Physical Chemistry and the Founding Director of the Linz Institute for Organic Solar Cells (LIOS) at the Johannes Kepler University of Linz/Austria.

He studied at the University of Vienna (Austria) and graduated as Ph.D. in Physics in 1989. After two years postdoctoral study at the University of Stuttgart (Germany)

he joined the Institute for Polymers and Organic Solids at the University of California, Santa Barbara, USA, led by Prof. Alan J. Heeger, Nobel Laureate in Chemistry in the year 2000. In Santa Barbara, Prof. Sariciftci invented the conjugated polymer and fullerene based "bulk heterojunction" solar cells and later on at Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria, his institute held the world record of efficiency of organic solar cells for three occasions (2001, 2003 and 2005) as documented by the NREL chart.

Prof. Sariciftci published more than 600 publications that received in excess of 94000 citations. He is one of the most cited scientists in material science (2011, Thompson Reuter ranking his as No: 14 of the world in Materials Science); Google Scholar currently ranks him with an h-index of 132. Prof. Sariciftci has composed 8 books and educated many academic and industrial scientists. He also initiated seven spin-off companies in the area of organic optoelectronics. He is recipient of several prizes among them the National Science Prize of Turkey 2006 and the Austrian Scientists of the year Prize for Research 2008. He received the Medal for Humanity of the City of Linz 2009 and the Kardinal Prize for Science of the Archbishop in Vienna 2010. In 2012 he was awarded the prestigious Wittgenstein Prize of Austria. He is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Chemistry (FRSC), Fellow of SPIE, and member of several societies such as American Chemical Society, Materials Research Society, Austrian Chemical Society and Austrian Physical Society. He was selected as corresponding member of the Academy of Science in Austria (ÖAW). Prof. Sariciftci has been awarded honorary doctorate by the Abo Academy in Finland in 2011 and University of Bucharest in Romania in 2012. Prof. Sariciftci received the TÜBA Science Prize of the Turkish Academy of Sciences (2015) and was selected as member of the Turkish Academy of Sciences in 2017. He received the Selcuk Yasar University Prize for Advancement of Science and Humanity in Turkey in 2020. In 2022 Prof. Sariciftci was selected as fellow of the Ethiopian Academy of Sciences for his services to education of scientists from Ethiopia.

Prof. Sariciftci's major contributions and research interests are in the fields of photoinduced optical, magnetic resonance and transport phenomena in semiconducting and metallic polymers.

Mihai Irimia-Vladu has been since 2019 University Assistant in the Institute of Physical Chemistry and Linz Institute of Organic Solar Cells of Johannes Kepler University in Linz, Austria, Austria.

He obtained his B.S. in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Craiova in 1997 and after three years of activity in industry, completed his Ph.D. under the guidance of Prof. Jeffrey W.

Fergus in the field of solid-state sensing, at the Materials Engineering Department of Auburn University, Alabama, in 2006. He moved to Johannes Kepler University in Linz, Austria as post-doctoral fellow, working within the research groups of Prof. Serdar Sariciftci and late Prof. Siegfried Bauer. In Linz, he was the initiator and principal investigator of “green” materials for organic electronics. From 2012 to 2019, Dr. Irimia-Vladu was Senior Scientist at Johanneum Research, Department of Materials in Weiz, Austria.

For his first worldwide demonstration of “edible electronics” in March 2011, he has been awarded in the year 2011 the “1st prize of Austrian Society for Environment and Technology” and has been named “Austrian of the day” by the regional newspaper in the Upper Austria region. Among other scientific discoveries that can be credited to him, one can name the first report of semiconducting properties of the historic dyes indigo and Tyrian purple, which helped open a new research field on hydrogen-bonded semiconductors.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have no conflict of interests to declare.

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